

Original Research

The Determinants of Stock Market Performance Among Registered Companies in Tanzania: A Case of Dar Es Salaam Stock Exchange

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to ascertain how sales growth affects the stock market performance of businesses listed on the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE). More specifically, the study determined the correlation between sales growth and stock market performance. A quantitative method was used to analyze the secondary data from 14 companies out of 28 registered with the DSE. Furthermore, the analysis of quantitative data using the Generalized Linear Equation Model (GLM), Mixed Generalized Linear Regression Model (MGLM), and Panel Regression Model (PRM) helped to obtain results for generalization. Findings indicated that sales growth had a statistically significant negative impact on the firm's performance by 0.01 according to the pooled GLM in Tanzania. The fixed and random effect model revealed a non-statistically significant effect despite the unbalanced panel effects; as a result, sales growth had a 0.516 negative influence on firm performance. As a result, the financial performance of the organization and sales growth were inversely related. The study recommended that companies registered with the DSE should well leverage so as to benefit from the performance competitiveness of the DSE public market.

Keywords: DSE, performances, sales growth, stock market.

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Introduction

Sales growth is a crucial determinant of stock market performance, as it reflects a company's ability to generate revenue and expand its market share. In Tanzania, the relationship between sales growth and stock market performance is particularly significant, as it can indicate the overall health of listed companies on the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE) (Pankratz et al., 2023). Companies experiencing robust sales growth often see increased investor confidence, which can drive up stock prices and enhance overall market performance (Egbunike & Okerekeoti, 2018). However, sales growth is one of the indicator of stock market performance and investment success of the previously years that can be used to forecast future growth and the company's ability to grow is demonstrated by its increase in sales which lead to great revenue as well as the company profits (Budiharjo, 2023).

Globally, the stock market performance was affected by 2009 economic crash, corona virus that caused Covid-19 pandemic as far as affecting the emerging stock markets (Endri et al., 2021; Yfanti, 2022). In the study by U-din (2022), it was proved that the Canadian stock market experienced a decline as a result of an increase in confirmed COVID-19 cases while in Australia the performance of stock exchange has improved due to the COVID-19 infection. COVID -19 period can seem to retarding calamity in stock market by measuring investment opportunities and potential losses in general.

In Africa Efficient performance of commercial banks listed on the Nairobi Securities exchange (NSE) in Kenya was reported to be influenced by effective net asset management (Access, 2024). Also, in this study highlights the critical role of managing assets efficiently and proper net assets can lead to improved profitability, better liquidity and overall financial stability for banks. However, according to (Chikwira & Mohammed, 2023). Investment is still the key driver of economic growth although resources allocation and mobilization are essential pre-requisites for investments, the stock exchange market and other financial intermediaries play a crucial role in ensuring liquidity for long term investors in Nigeria.

Comprehending the factors that influencing the performance of registered firms on stock market and their interplay enables investors, analysts and the general public to make well-informed judgements regarding stock market investments. Stock market is regarded as a marketplace dealing with stock market assets, where traders purchase and sell commodities, derivatives, foreign exchange, stocks and bonds. Tanzania, a diverse and rapidly growing East African economy, has been attracting increasing attention from investors and corporations, both domestic and international (R.P. et al., 2024). The study by Marobhe & Pastory, (2020), found that, the Stock Exchange in Dar es Salaam (DSE) Tanzania is a fastest growing economic section in Africa in securities exchange. The exchange market became operationalized in 1998 after being incorporated in 1996 as a private company limited. Principally, the Capital Markets and Securities Act of 1994, amended in 1997, 2000 and 2010 govern the securities industry in the country. The ability to develop effective and efficient stock market could impede the empirical growth of a healthy economy, as stock market expansion is beneficial for both short and long-term resource mobilization (Kamazima & Kebaso Omurwa, 2018).

Prior research has shown that sales growth can positively influence stock prices by indicating robust business operations and future profitability (Sangawe, 2014; Ye et al., 2020). However, the relationship between sales growth and stock market performance varies based on market conditions and company-specific factors (Kılıç et al., 2022; Lee, 2023; Zaw Moe, 2023). This growth typically leads to higher profitability, which positively impacts investor sentiment, driving up the stock price (Chen et al., 2022). In emerging markets like Tanzania, sales growth is particularly important (Utouh & Kitole, 2024). A study by (Mkhize, 2022) found that firms with high sales growth saw significant increases in stock prices compared to those with stagnant sales.

Thus, the study aimed to answer the research question: “*What is the influence of sales growth on the stock market performance of registered companies on the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE) in Tanzania?*” Additionally, the study includes well-defined hypotheses to guide the analysis:

H₁: There is a positive relationship between sales growth and stock market performance.

H₂: Leverage negatively impacts stock market performance.

This is a compelling research question because understanding the relationship between sales growth and stock market performance is crucial for both investors and policymakers. Investigating how sales growth impacts the performance of companies listed on the DSE will provide valuable insights into the factors that drive stock prices and overall market trends (Nkuru & Raphael, 2023). For investors, sales growth is a key signal of a company’s ability to generate revenue, expand its market share, and sustain operations, which in turn boosts investor confidence (Okonkwo, 2024). A strong sales performance indicates not only short-term profitability but also long-term growth potential, making it a critical element in investment decision-making (Ternova & Zharova, 2023). This study sheds light on how investors react to companies' sales performance, helping them assess the viability of future investments.

In the context of emerging markets like Tanzania, the impact of sales growth on stock market performance is especially important due to the unique economic conditions. Emerging markets are characterized by high growth potential but also heightened risks, such as market volatility, limited liquidity, and regulatory challenges (Sengera, 2021). Understanding how sales growth influences stock performance helps both domestic and foreign investors better navigate these markets and identify profitable opportunities (SHELEMO, 2023). In addition, Tanzania’s stock market is still developing, and its performance can offer insights into how market structure, investor behavior, and company fundamentals interact in economies undergoing transformation (Mwakabumbe, 2023).

The study also examines other key determinants of stock performance, such as leverage and asset tangibility, which are grounded in existing financial literature. Leverage, for instance, reflects the extent to which companies rely on debt financing to fuel operations and growth (Change, 2021). While moderate leverage can amplify returns, excessive debt levels may signal financial instability, which could negatively affect

investor sentiment and stock prices (Mwenda, 2021). Therefore, testing the relationship between leverage and stock market performance allows the study to offer nuanced insights into the risks and rewards of debt-financed growth strategies (Ngole & Mabonesho, 2023).

Asset tangibility is another relevant determinant because it reflects the proportion of a company's total assets that are physical, such as property, equipment, and inventory (Sengera, 2021). Higher tangibility can enhance borrowing capacity, as tangible assets serve as collateral for loans. This can impact a company's capital structure and indirectly influence stock market performance by affecting creditworthiness, operational efficiency, and growth potential. Including asset tangibility in the analysis adds depth to the research by considering how the composition of a firm's assets can influence both its financial stability and investor perceptions.

By examining these determinants sales growth, leverage, and asset tangibility the study provides a comprehensive view of stock market performance in Tanzania. This approach is particularly relevant for companies, investors, analysts, and policymakers seeking to understand how firm-level factors shape market outcomes. The results of this research will also contribute to existing academic literature on emerging markets by providing context-specific findings that highlight the unique dynamics of the Tanzanian economy and stock exchange.

Literature Review

In its wide context, sales involve various activities such as prospecting, lead generation, pitching, negotiating, and closing deals (Batchimeg, 2017). In fact, effective sales include the strong convincing strategies and techniques that are essential for businesses to attract customers, drive revenue growth, and achieve their stock market goals (A et al., 2024; Taruvinga, 2024). The influence of sales growth on the stock market performance of registered stock market exchange companies is a critical factor to consider (Conference et al., 2024). Sales growth is a key performance indicator for businesses, often seen as a measure of a company's ability to increase revenue over time (Mandasari, 2023). Prior research has shown that sales growth can positively influence stock prices by indicating robust business operations and future profitability (Sangawe, 2014; Ye et al., 2020).

However, companies with high sales growth may also face higher stock price volatility (Rauf et al., 2023). This is because investors have heightened expectations, and any failure to meet sales targets can result in sharp declines in stock prices (Meliana et al., 2022). On the other hand, exceeding expectations can lead to significant price increases (City-redi, 2023; Conrad Diegel, 2023). Sales growth typically signals a company's ability to expand its market share and improve profitability (Arnaz & Nugroho, 2024). Investors often view growing sales as a predictor of higher future earnings, driving up demand for the company's stock and thus increasing its price (Bashir et al., 2023; Yadav et al., 2023). Many investors, particularly in mature markets, prefer companies that offer regular dividends, as it provides them with steady returns (Mandasari, 2023; Sholeha, 2023). Consequently, companies with high dividend payouts often see more stable stock

prices, as dividend-seeking investors are less likely to sell their shares during market downturns (Fadhilah & Widajantie, 2024).

Companies with strong sales growth typically experience higher levels of revenue, which can lead to increased profitability and shareholder value; however, stagnant or declining sales growth may indicate underlying issues that could negatively impact stock market performance, such as market saturation, competitive pressures, or operational inefficiencies (A et al., 2024; Taruvinga, 2024). According to (Hermuningsih, 2019), "the company's increased profits would indicate that the company's financial performance was getting better and the company's prospects going forward became promising." However, the relationship between sales growth and stock market performance can vary based on market conditions and company-specific factors (Kılıç et al., 2022; Lee, 2023; Zaw Moe, 2023). Firms with a higher proportion of tangible assets tend to have more stable stock prices because investors view tangible assets as more secure and easier to liquidate in times of financial distress (Tasneem, 2024). Investors prefer companies with a strong base of physical assets, particularly in industries such as manufacturing, real estate, and utilities (Feng et al., 2021).

Influence of Leverage and Asset Tangibility

In addition to sales growth, this study examines leverage and asset tangibility as independent variables influencing stock market performance. Leverage reflects a company's use of debt to finance operations, and its relationship with stock market performance is critical. While moderate leverage can enhance returns, excessive debt levels may raise concerns about financial stability, potentially deterring investors (Khémiri et al., 2024). This study aims to explore how varying leverage levels impact investor sentiment, stock prices, and ultimately, market performance.

Asset tangibility is another important variable as it indicates the proportion of a company's assets that are physical and can be liquidated in times of financial distress. Higher levels of tangible assets tend to correlate with more stable stock prices, as investors often perceive tangible assets as safer (Fulfillment & Tasneem, 2015). This is especially relevant in industries such as manufacturing and real estate, where physical assets play a crucial role in operations. Liu et al. (2023) suggest companies with a strong base of physical assets are more attractive to investors, particularly in emerging market where financial system may be less developed.

Empirical Literature on Emerging Markets

The literature highlights the unique factors at play in emerging stock markets, where conventional investment strategies may not apply. For example, research by (Makina, 2005) emphasizes that investor behavior in these markets is often driven by a combination of domestic and global factors, including economic indicators, political stability, and market liquidity. Additionally, emerging markets typically exhibit higher volatility and less predictability than developed markets (Soni, n.d.). This volatility underscores the importance of understanding how firm-specific characteristics, such as sales growth, leverage, and asset tangibility, influence stock performance.

Emerging market studies have indicated that investor perceptions of risk and return are fundamentally different compared to developed markets, which can significantly affect stock performance (Soni, n.d.). For example, in their examination of African stock markets, (Boamah, 2015) noted that firms with higher betas are expected to demonstrate strong sales growth to justify the additional risk investors are assuming. This highlights the critical nature of sales growth in attracting investment in contexts where market conditions are uncertain and potentially volatile.

The study deployed the Capital Pricing Model (CAPM), which emphasizes “how risk and expected return are related to each other when pricing risky assets.” Its predictions are based on the notion that investors should be compensated for the risk they take on when making investments in particular assets, as well as the concept of the time value of money. By using CAPM, investors can determine whether a company's stock is priced appropriately given its level of risk compared to the overall market.

By using CAPM, investors can determine whether a company's stock is priced appropriately given its level of risk compared to the overall market (Rizwan Qamar et al., 2014). Companies with higher beta values are expected to have higher returns to compensate for the increased risk, according to CAPM (Kisman & Shintabelle, 2015). Understanding and applying CAPM can assist investors in making informed decisions about their investment portfolios and help companies evaluate their cost of equity and overall performance in the stock market (Alqisie & Alqurran, 2021). Fama & French (2006) suggest that companies with a higher beta often need to demonstrate strong sales growth to justify the additional risk investors are taking on.

CAPM's insights into systematic risk (market risk) versus unsystematic risk (firm-specific risk) are critical for companies targeting sales growth, companies in industries with high market sensitivity may experience fluctuations in sales tied to market conditions (Obande, 2022). For instance, companies in cyclical sectors like consumer goods or technology, with higher betas, may experience more volatile sales growth tied to broader economic conditions. CAPM, therefore, helps investors and companies to adjust expectations around sales growth based on macroeconomic factors.

The implications of the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) for the performance of registered companies in the stock market lie in its ability to help investors and analysts assess the expected return of a company's stock based on its risk profile.

Methodology

The positivism approach with a quantitative case study design was employed, involving secondary data from 14 out of 28 registered companies to DSE. The study used random sampling to select 14 companies from the DSE. Additionally, sales growth was an independent variable, while stock market performance among registered firms was a dependent variable. This study deployed inferential analysis, namely the generalized linear model (GLM), the mixed generalized linear model (MGLM), and the panel linear regression model (PLRM). All analyses were conducted using STATA version 15.

In the context of stock market performance, the dependent variable might not always follow a normal distribution and could exhibit skewness or kurtosis (Cain et al., 2017). The GLM accommodates this by allowing for different error distributions making it an appropriate choice for modeling stock performance, which can be highly volatile and may not be normally distributed (Wilson et al., 2024). The GLM's ability to model various distributions makes it a suitable option for capturing the potential nonlinear relationship between sales growth and stock market performance, allowing for more robust inferences. In this study, companies listed on the DSE likely exhibit individual-specific characteristics (e.g., sector differences, company size, or management practices) that might influence their stock performance independently of sales growth. These unobserved heterogeneities can be modeled as random effects in the MGLM. By accounting for both the fixed effects (e.g., sales growth) and random effects (e.g., company-specific factors), the MGLM allows the model to capture variability across companies more accurately (Peterson, 2021). The MGLM enables the researcher to account for inter-company variability, improving the robustness of the model and preventing biased estimates that could result from ignoring the differences among companies.

Since the study involves data from multiple companies over time, a panel data approach is essential to control for both company-specific and time-specific effects. The PLRM is well-suited for handling this kind of data, allowing the researcher to account for the possibility that the impact of sales growth on stock performance could vary not only between companies but also over time (Oikonomou, 2023). The PLRM enables the study to model both individual company effects and time effects, thus improving the precision of the estimates and capturing dynamic changes in the relationship between sales growth and stock market performance over time.

While GLM, MGLM, and panel regression models are chosen for their flexibility, ability to handle categorical outcomes, and robustness in controlling for individual and time-specific effects, it is acknowledged that dynamic panel models like GMM could provide additional insights, particularly for examining temporal relationships and addressing potential endogeneity in stock performance data (Bandyopadhyay, 2022). In future research, considering dynamic panel models might enhance the analysis, particularly in understanding how historical performance influences current results. This approach would allow for a more nuanced exploration of the factors impacting stock market performance in the DSE, aligning the methodology with the complexities inherent in financial data.

The mathematical model specification delineating the relationship between independent variables and the dependent variable was structured into two components. The initial component pertained to the execution of pooled cross-sectional analysis, while the subsequent component pertained to the execution of panel data analysis. The models are articulated as follows: The generalized linear model (GLM) serves as an extension of the linear regression model, assuming that the predictors exhibit linear relationships. In instances where certain predictors do not demonstrate a linear relationship with the dependent variable, GLM was employed, utilizing the Poisson distribution and the log link functions. It was assumed that the dependent variable (return on assets, or ROA) adheres to the Poisson distribution. The mathematical representation is as follows:

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_3 x_3 + \beta_4 x_4 + \beta_5 x_5 + \beta_6 x_6 + \beta_7 x_7 + \epsilon_i$$

Where: β_0 as the intercept

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_7$ Are coefficient

x_1 as the leverage, x_2 as sales growth, x_3 as firm size, x_4 as firm age, x_5 as assets tangibility, x_6 as liquidity and x_7 as corporate tax ratio. The ϵ_i represents the error term showing the effect of variables not accounted in the model.

Ever since the dependent variable Y may be restricted and the variance may not necessarily depend on the mean, then the GLM was introduced to relax these weaknesses. The corresponding equation, expressed as a link function is presented as here below.

$$n_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{1i} + \beta_2 x_{2i} + \beta_3 x_{3i} + \beta_4 x_{4i} + \beta_5 x_{5i} + \beta_6 x_{6i} + \beta_7 x_{7i} + \epsilon_i$$

Where: $\epsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$

Based on the MGLM, we assumed that observations were nested within companies. Therefore, the mathematical representation corresponding to this MGLM was as follows:

$$Y_{ij} = \beta_{0j} + \beta_1 x_{1j} + \beta_2 x_{2j} + \beta_3 x_{3j} + \beta_4 x_{4j} + \beta_5 x_{5j} + \beta_6 x_{6j} + \beta_7 x_{7j} + \epsilon_i$$

Where: the intercept β_{0j} is allowed to vary across companies $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 14$

The PRM with a fixed and random effect model was also constructed. The fixed effect model works under the assumption that the differences between cross sections or individuals may be assessed using an intercept. This is accommodated when the dummy variable approach is adopted. In the random effect model, normally the difference observed between intercepts of companies is accommodated by the error terms of each corresponding company. The model is presented as follows:

The fixed effect model is stipulated as follows:

$$y_{it} = \beta_i + \beta' X_{1t} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where: $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$ for companies and $t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, T$ for time periods

Then, the random effect model also known as the error component model (ECM) was stipulated as follows:

$$y_{it} = \beta + \beta' X_{1t} + u_i + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where: u_i is the individual company residual and ϵ_{it} is the overall residual combining cross sectional and time series.

Results and Discussion

In this study, the data comes from 14 companies, namely: CRDB Bank, Dar es Salaam Commercial Bank (DCB), Maendeleo Bank, Mkombozi Bank, Mwalimu Commercial Bank, National Microfinance Bank (NMB), Swala Gas and Oil Company Ltd. (SWALA), Precision Air Services PLC (PAL), Tanzania Cigarette Co. Ltd. (TCC), Tanzania Breweries Ltd. (TBL), Tanzania Portland Cement Co. Ltd. (TWIGA), SWISSPORT Tanzania Ltd. (SWISSPORT), Tanzania Tea Packers Ltd. (TATEPA), and TOL Gases Ltd. (TOL).

This research examined the factors influencing firm performance by utilizing return on assets (ROA) as the dependent variable and three primary independent variables: sales growth, firm size, and leverage. Additionally, control variables such as firm age, corporate tax ratio, liquidity, and asset tangibility were included in the analysis. The study progressed from descriptive to inferential methodologies. The findings are presented in a sequential manner as follows: the sample consisted of 14 companies, each with 8 observations, resulting in a total of 112 observations. The minimum ROA observed was -163.77, while the maximum ROA recorded was 84.42. The mean ROA was 9.17, indicating that, on average, company performance was 9.19; however, some companies exhibited negative ROA, indicating poor performance. The mean value of within-firm ROA was 20.78, and the mean between-firm ROA was 19.84. Please refer to Table 1 for detailed information.

Table 1. Descriptive analysis of study variables

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Observations		
ROA overall	9.170	28.292	-163.770	84.420	N	=	112
Between	19.837	-17.433	50.705	n	=		14
Within	20.779	-137.168	111.022	T	=		8
Corporate. Overall	0.224	0.202	-0.300	1.134	N	=	112
Between	0.098	0.048	0.333	n	=		14
Within	0.179	-0.190	1.259	T	=		8
Liquidity overall	6.818	10.785	.04	67.690	N	=	112
Between	7.547	0.248	19.251	n	=		14
Within	7.934	-9.244	60.850	T	=		8
Leverage overall	2.856	9.944	-25.900	96.411	N	=	112
Between	3.943	-2.442	12.607	n	=		14
Within	9.183	-20.602	86.660	T	=		8
Asset overall	0.407	0.321	0.007	0.911	N	=	112
Between	0.308	0.027	0.860	n	=		14
Within	0.117	0.231	1.151	T	=		8
Sales grow overall	1.519	12.630	-0.999	132.525	N	=	112
Between	5.136	-0.033	19.355	n	=		14
Within	11.610	-18.771	114.689	T	=		8
Firm size overall	7.826	1.143	4.679	9.734	N	=	112
Between	0.803	6.377	8.887	n	=		14
Within	0.839	5.295	10.316	T	=		8
Firm age overall	26	18.636	0	68	N	=	112
Between	19.106	3.5	64.500	n	=		14
Within	2.302	22.500	29.500	T	=		8

In serving the purpose of this study sales growth were used as the main determinants of stock market performance among registered Companies in Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange.

Influence of Sales Growth on Stock Market Performance

The study revealed that sales growth had a negative effect on the company's stock market performance using the pooled cross-sectional analysis as presented in Table 2. Considering only independent variables (model 1), it was revealed that for each unit increase in sales growth, firms' stock market performance had a statistically significant decrease of 0.007 at $p < 0.001$. A similar statistically significant decrease of 0.011 and 0.0108 was revealed when adjusting for other independent variables, including company name (model 2) and year (model 3), respectively.

Table 2. Pooled analysis using GLM

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Corporate tax ratio	2.678***(12.55)	-0.0447(-0.12)	0.0277(0.07)
Liquidity	-0.0313***(-5.24)	0.0240**(2.72)	0.0203*(2.30)
Leverage	-0.373***(-20.51)	-0.147**(-2.77)	-0.142**(-2.63)
Asset tangibility	-0.864***(-5.69)	0.277(0.82)	0.104(0.29)
Sales growth	-0.00680***(-3.71)	-0.0111***(-5.22)	-0.0108***(-4.06)
Firm size	0.0611*(2.43)	0.239***(5.97)	0.213***(3.75)
Firm age	-0.00284(-1.73)	-0.0622***(-4.16)	-0.0801***(-3.36)
Company			
1.CRDB		1	1
2.DCB		-0.591(-1.47)	-0.690(-1.62)
3.Maendeleo Bank		-1.632**(-3.14)	-1.869**(-3.09)
4.Mkombozi Bank		-0.451(-1.05)	-0.649(-1.28)
5.Mwalimu C/Bank		0.156(0.52)	0.151(0.50)
6.NMB		-0.112(-0.12)	-0.0678(-0.07)
7.SWALA		2.133*** (4.40)	2.517*** (4.16)
8.PAL		1.894** (3.14)	1.533* (2.13)
9.TCC		3.411*** (7.55)	3.629*** (7.14)
10.TBL		-0.240(-0.37)	-0.0824(-0.12)
11.TWIGA		1.792*** (3.76)	1.881*** (3.79)
12. SWISSPORT		4.079*** (7.36)	4.638*** (5.86)
13.TATEPA		3.839*** (5.50)	4.703*** (4.27)
14.TOL		3.863*** (6.22)	4.574*** (4.88)
Year			
2011			1
2012.			0.132(1.42)
2013.			-0.108(-1.09)
2014.			0.270**(2.60)
2015.			0.171(1.34)
2016.			0.0586(0.40)
2017.			0.200(1.44)

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
2018.			Ocdssddsds
_cons	2.875***(15.22)	0.616(0.87)	1.106(1.18)
N	89	89	89
t statistics in parentheses			
=** p<0.05	** p<0.01	*** p<0.001"	

Similarly, the MGLM revealed that sales growth had a statistically significant negative effect of 0.01 at $p < 0.001$ as presented in table 3.

Table 3. Mixed Generalized Linear Mode.

mixed-effects GLM Family:		Number of Obs	=	89
Link:	poison			
group variable:	log	Number of groups	=	14
	Company new	Obs per group:		
		min	=	2
		avg	=	6.4
		max	=	8
Integration method	mvaghermite	Integration pts.	=	7
Log likelihood =	-311.77845	Wald chi2 (7)	=	117.77
		Prob > chi 2	=	0.0000

ROA_new	Coef.	Std.err	z	p>/z/	(95% conf. Interval)	
Corporate tax ratio	-.0123178	.371509	-0.03	0.974	-.7404621	.7158264
Liquidity	.0217495	.0086712	2.51	0.012	.0047543	.0387448
Leverage	-.1792324	.0496853	-3. 61	0.000	-.2766139	-.0818509
Asset tangibility	.2223485	.3323006	0,67	0.503	-.4289488	.8736458
Sales growth	-.0120542	.0021046	-5.73	0.000	-.0161791	-.0079292
Firm size	.2619019	.039213	6.68	0.000	-1850459	.338758
firm age	-.039582	.0147326	-2.69	0.007	-.0684374	-.0106867
_cons	1.286684	.6895076	1.87	0.062	-.0647259	2.638094

Company

Var (_cons)	2.213396	1.067529
	.8600456	5.696352

LR test vs. Poisson model: $\text{chibar2} (01) = 456.99$

Prob >= $\text{chibar2} = 0.0000$

Additionally, the fixed and random effect models as presented in table 4 revealed that sales growth had a positive, however being non-statistically significant at 5% level using the xtreg command. Using the xtregar command, we revealed that sales growth had a negative effect on the stock market performance of stock market exchange companies at $p < 0.001$ as evidence by a reduction of 0.52 on stock market performance for each unit increase of sales.

Table 4. Fixed and random effect modelling of the determinants of stock market performance

Variables	Estimates from Xtreg		Estimates from Xtgar
	Fixed	Random	
corporatetaxratio	-0.326(-0.03)	11.85(1.01)	-0.873 (-0.08)
Liquidity	-0.0437(-0.18)	-0.298(-1.10)	-0.0901(-0.81)
Leverage	-0.129(-0.65)	-0.129(-0.56)	-0.0812(-0.09)
Asset tangibility	-84.07***(-4.93)	-41.10***(-3.35)	10.34(0.89)
Sales growth	0.220(1.30)	0.0815(0.44)	-0.516***(-5.60)
Firm size	-0.375(-0.15)	3.077(1.31)	3.248**(2.91)
Firm age	-1.354(-1.54)	0.738*** (3.42)	-2.105**(-2.99)
_cons	81.98*(2.42)	-17.72(-0.94)	53.26**(3.28)
Sigma_u	57.3533	7.95	45.029
Sigma_e	18.9788	18.9788	7.26
rho	0.9013	0.1493	0.975
Rho_ar			0.3302
Test that all u _i =0:	F (13,91) =8.13, F=0.000		F (13,54) =12.48, F=0.000
Modified Bhargava et al. Durbin-Watson			1.3579
Baltagi-Wu LBI			1.9948
N	112	112	75
t statistics in parentheses			
=** p<0.05	** p<0.01	*** p<0.001"	

The results on the influence of sales growth on the stock market performance of registered stock market exchange companies are inversely proportional to Batchimeg (2017) who found the regression results of stock market ratios ROA, ROE, and ROS on earnings per share and return on costs. The regression results shown a significant positive relation on stock market performance of an organization. In addition, Babarinde et al. (2024) revealed that ATM, POS, mobile based, and web-based digital finance transactions had a positive and significant impact on the stock market capitalization ratio in Nigeria. Nevertheless, Ozturk and Karabulut (2020) revealed the earnings per Share (EPS) and Price-to-Sales ratios to have significant effects on technology and telecommunication companies' stock returns. This kind of analysis bare a crucial importance that companies need to analyze the beneath underlying reasons for the negative relationship of sales growth on stock market performance as summarized in figure 1. Nevertheless, appropriate measures should be taken to challenge this relationship.

Figure 1. Sales Growth

When sales growth suggests the negatively impacts on companies' stock market performance, it typically means that despite an increase in sales revenue, the company is experiencing challenges that are affecting its overall stock market health. The challenges such as declining profit margins, increased operating expenses, inefficient cost management, poor inventory management or any other competent reason. In that regard, this negative relation reveals inability of a company to translate its sales growth into improved cash flow, which in turn impact its stock market performance in a negative way.

Negative Relationship between Sales Growth and Stock Market Performance

The negative correlation between sales growth and stock market performance suggests that, despite increasing revenues, companies on the DSE struggle with underlying issues that undermine their market performance. These challenges could include: Declining profit margins, increased operating expenses, Inefficient cost management, Cash flow challenges

This relationship signals potential inefficiencies within companies that need to be addressed. A negative impact of sales growth may raise investor concerns, leading to a decline in stock prices, even when revenues are rising. Management efficiency, cost control, and profitability become critical indicators of stock performance in such cases. The research implications concerning the assessment of stock market performance in Tanzania, with a specific focus on companies listed on Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE), encompasses both practical and policy considerations.

Practical Implications

The study's results have important practical implications for companies and investors, highlighting the need for strategic adjustments to ensure sustainable market performance. Investors may interpret the negative relationship between sales growth and stock

performance as a red flag, suggesting deeper operational inefficiencies such as excessive costs, weak cash flow management, or declining profit margins. This could lead to reduced confidence in a company's prospects, triggering stock sell-offs and contributing to increased volatility in the market. For companies, these findings emphasize the importance of reassessing their operational strategies to address the underlying factors causing poor market performance despite revenue growth. Firms must focus not only on expanding sales but also on managing costs effectively, improving cash flow, and ensuring profitability to align with investor expectations.

Additionally, the Tanzanian stock market poses unique challenges that further complicate the relationship between growth and stock performance. Economic uncertainties, such as inflation, currency fluctuations, and policy changes, create an unpredictable environment that can impact company valuations. Fluctuating market conditions, along with relatively low levels of investor participation, mean that even well-performing companies may struggle to achieve the market valuation they deserve. Limited investor participation also restricts the pool of capital available, increasing competition for investment and heightening the pressure on companies to demonstrate sustainable growth.

To maintain investor trust and sustain market performance, companies need to adopt a more holistic approach to growth. This involves balancing revenue expansion with profitability, improving operational efficiency, and effectively communicating growth strategies to stakeholders. By translating growth into tangible outcomes, such as higher dividends or reinvestment in value-generating activities, companies can foster investor confidence. Ultimately, aligning growth strategies with long-term profitability and sustainable performance will enhance market valuations, reduce the likelihood of stock sell-offs, and contribute to a more resilient market environment.

Policy Implications

The findings suggest several important policy implications for improving stock market performance on the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE). Regulatory reforms to align growth with market performance are essential, as the negative impact of sales growth on stock performance may indicate a separation between corporate strategies and investor expectations. Policymakers, particularly the Capital Markets and Securities Authority (CMSA), should introduce frameworks that promote transparency in firms' growth strategies. Requiring firms to provide regular disclosures of forward-looking financial indicators can help align market expectations with corporate performance, reducing volatility and improving valuation.

Furthermore, promoting investor education and awareness is critical. The findings suggest that investors may not fully appreciate the value of long-term growth, highlighting the need for education initiatives focused on interpreting financial data, market trends, and how corporate growth impacts stock performance. This could foster a culture of long-term investment over short-term speculation. At the same time, incentivizing sustainable growth strategies is vital. Firms should be encouraged to adopt balanced growth strategies that align revenue growth with profitability. Policymakers

could offer incentives, such as tax relief or subsidies, to companies that demonstrate such sustainable practices, motivating them to avoid purely sales-driven growth.

To attract both domestic and foreign investment, enhancing market confidence is crucial. The government should introduce policies that stabilize the market by reviewing dividend policies and improving corporate governance practices. A better alignment between sales growth, market performance, and dividend distribution will help attract long-term investors and support the market's sustainable development. Moreover, strengthening corporate governance standards can address potential weaknesses in internal structures that may have contributed to the negative relationship between growth and performance. Regulators should ensure that firms align growth strategies with profitability, innovation, and efficiency, boosting investor confidence and improving stock valuations.

The research also suggests the need for sector-specific policies to improve performance, as the impact of sales growth may vary across industries. Tailored regulatory adjustments for sectors like financial services, agriculture, and manufacturing can enhance firms' responsiveness to market dynamics and investor expectations. Lastly, encouraging the diversification of revenue sources is essential to mitigate risks associated with fluctuating sales. Policymakers could promote this diversification by providing favorable regulations or financing options, helping firms achieve greater stability and increasing their attractiveness to investors. These policy measures collectively aim to foster a more stable, transparent, and efficient stock market, ultimately contributing to Tanzania's economic growth.

VIF (Variance Inflation Factor)

VIF indicates the degree of multicollinearity among the independent variables considered in the particular regression model. The higher the VIF suggests greater correlation with other variables, which can inflate the variance of the coefficient estimates. The VIF is the positive value greater or equal to one, the values above 10 implies the presence of multicollinearity (Shantha Kumari, 2008; Tsagris & Pandis, 2021). On the other hand, the $1/VIF$ represents the proportion of variance not inflated due to multicollinearity. A value closer to 1 indicates lower inflation. For instance, based on Firm size ($VIF = 7.73$, $1/VIF=0.12931$): this indicates moderate multicollinearity with VIF values above 5 but below 10 while Asset tangibility ($VIF = 4.76$, $1/VIF=0.21001$) indicates low to moderate multicollinearity, generally acceptable. Furthermore, Sales growth ($VIF = 1.09$, $1/VIF=0.91581$) implies very low multicollinearity, indicating high stability. In general, the Mean VIF was below 5 for each model, suggesting the moderate multicollinearity across the model, but overall, the VIF values are manageable as presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5. Assessment of multicollinearity between independent variables

Variable	Fixed effect model		Random effect model		Xtregar model	
	VIF	1/VIF	VIF	1/VIF	VIF	1/VIF
Firm size	7.73	0.129339	7.73	0.129339	8.21	0.12180268
Firm age	5.16	0.193797	5.16	0.193797	6.09	0.164279
Asset tangibility	4.76	0.209986	4.76	0.209986	5.47	0.182727
Corporate tax	2.43	0.411633	2.43	0.411633	4.61	0.216810
Leverage	1.12	0.893913	1.12	0.893913	2.72	0.367359
Liquidity	2.33	0.429687	2.33	0.429687	2.72	0.367388
Sales growth	1.09	0.915817	1.09	0.915817	1.13	0.882097
<i>Mean VIF</i>	<i>3.52</i>		<i>3.52</i>		<i>4.421429</i>	

VIF < 5: Generally, indicates no serious multicollinearity.

Discovering Statistics Using IBM SPSS Statistics (Relations & Bähre, 2021). Sage Publications. This book discusses VIF and suggests that values below 5 indicate a low risk of multicollinearity.

VIF between 5 and 10: Suggests moderate multicollinearity; it's advisable to investigate further.

Basic Econometrics. McGraw-Hill (Kami et al., 2013). This text explains that VIF values in this range can indicate moderate multicollinearity that may need attention.

VIF > 10: Indicates high multicollinearity, which may distort regression results and should be addressed.

"A Caution Regarding Rules of Thumb for Variance Inflation Factors (Johnston et al., 2018)." *Quality & Quantity*, 41(5), 673-690. This article discusses the implications of high VIF values and the common threshold of 10 for concern regarding multicollinearity.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study concludes that a negative correlation exists between sales growth and stock market performance among companies listed on the Dar es Salaam Stock Exchange (DSE). The pooled cross-sectional analysis revealed that each incremental increase in sales growth resulted in a statistically significant decline in stock market performance. This indicates that sales growth alone is insufficient to enhance market valuation, highlighting the need for firms to adopt a balanced approach that integrates growth with sound financial management.

To improve stock market valuation, companies must focus on several key strategies. Profitability should be prioritized over mere expansion to align with market expectations. Strong cash flow management is critical for sustaining operations and building investor confidence. Firms should also communicate value through transparent financial reporting, emphasizing how growth efforts translate into long-term returns. Targeted investments in high-return areas, coupled with efforts to improve customer experience

and strengthen brand positioning, will help create sustainable revenue streams. Additionally, active engagement with the investor community through meetings, conferences, and proactive communication is necessary to manage expectations and foster trust. Adopting a holistic strategy that balances profitability, operational efficiency, and strategic decision-making is essential for long-term market success.

Future research could enhance understanding by comparing the performance of DSE-listed firms with companies on other East African stock exchanges, providing insights into regional competitiveness. Exploring qualitative factors such as investor sentiment, corporate governance, and leadership will offer deeper insights into stock performance. Additionally, the impact of digital trading platforms, algorithmic trading, and financial technology on stock markets presents important areas for future exploration.

This study encountered challenges, including difficulties in selecting appropriate data analysis methods and limited proficiency with STATA software, which affected the analysis. Future studies could address these limitations by using advanced data tools and mixed methods approaches to enhance the reliability of findings. The study also emphasizes the need for actionable recommendations for firms and policymakers. Companies should adopt cost-efficiency measures to ensure growth does not erode profitability, revise dividend policies to attract investors, and align executive compensation with shareholder interests. Developing sector-specific strategies, particularly for high-growth industries like manufacturing and financial services, is also essential.

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